

IMPROVING THE CONTENT OF TRAINING OF EDUCATION SYSTEM EMPLOYEES IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract. *In the article, in the conditions of the innovative development of the society, the content of the training of the employees of the education system, especially the teachers of the science of education, was briefly described. Today, information was given that each pedagogue will develop his activities, improve professional knowledge and skills, and be regulated by ways of summarizing his activities based on regulatory legal documents.*

Keywords: *professional competence, phenomenal activity, activity, adaptability*

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the topic. Today, every pedagogue should develop his activities based on regulatory legal documents, improve his professional knowledge and skills, and regulate his activities with methods of generalization.

At the stage of mastering and improving professional competences, stabilization of normative activity, formation of professional position, as well as interconnected complexes of knowledge, skills and qualifications are carried out.

Personal qualities. It leads to the improvement of the most optimal method of activity at the creative level by developing it.

The formation of indispensable professional qualities of a teacher continues at the mastery stage.

A person who demonstrates phenomenal activity applies, changes, and improves the established methods of activity, i.e. raises it to a higher level of mastery to creative activity, which leads to further activation of the individual.

What is responsibility?

Why do we use it in our life and can we use it correctly?

Responsibility is the ability of each person to feel some duties and responsibilities towards himself.

That is, to fulfill their duties seriously in the family, society and other areas.

Responsibility is the ability and willingness of a person to answer for every word, action and work.

Responsibilities include:

In front of a person's actions and words: for example, to carry out planned activities, to take care of one's health, to own one's property;

In front of family and friends: for example, to protect their loved ones, show respect, affection and mutual support;

In front of the community: for example, to follow the laws of the country, one's rights and obligations, to take care of others in the neighborhood, at school, to study well in order to be a child worthy of the Motherland, etc.

Every year, 7% of people around the world change their careers due to various life challenges.

REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

In the developed countries of the world, the quality of education is primarily determined by the level of formation of the intellectual potential of personnel, professional initiative and professional responsibility.

The manifestation of professional responsibility can be divided into the following aspects.

- The person's attitude to work;
- Attitude towards oneself;
- To the management process;
- According to the nature of the character;
- emotional-volitional characteristics.

The following conclusions can be made based on the analysis and generalization of the psychological and pedagogical research, which revealed various aspects of the phenomenon of the development of flexibility competence:

1) The development of flexibility competence can be considered in terms of the following different approaches: as an activity; as a personality characteristic; as a person's ability; as an acmeological characteristic of the subject's activity.

He revealed the concept of flexibility competence development as a personal-activity approach related to personal ability, self-organization in professional activity.

In the acmeological approach, the development of flexibility competence is considered as the highest level of professional ability [35].

The concept of flexibility competence development competence as an activity implies a continuous (if necessary, repetitive) cycle of motivation, professional activity design, project implementation and independent evaluation of results.

DISCUSSIONS

In this cycle, the reflexive component is the main one. Its system-forming link means a critical reconstruction of the causes of real potential difficulties and a value-targeted evaluation of ways to eliminate them.

The ability to develop flexibility competence as a personal characteristic manifests intellectual, emotional and volitional character traits. To develop the flexibility competence of teachers in education, to create the necessary pedagogical conditions to ensure their professional and personal improvement, to retrain pedagogues. determines the main goal of developing specialist competence by modernizing its content and structure, determining its pedagogical-psychological conditions, and developing a quality control and evaluation mechanism.

In conducting our research, the personal-activity approach is of particular importance, in which the concept of the development of flexibility competence is considered simultaneously as an activity related to increasing the effectiveness of solving professional issues, and as a personal characteristic.

In our opinion, the skills of developing and managing the competence of flexibility in professional activity, which represent the skills of using personal intellectual and emotional-

volitional characteristics in solving professional issues, show the following personal characteristics:

- reasonable setting of goals;
- planning one's activities;
- resolute activity in mobilizing flexibility competence and achieving results;
- criteria for evaluating the results of their actions.

The results of the research revealing the essence of the development of the flexibility competence of the education teacher as a characteristic of the professional qualification are presented.

It should be concluded that every responsible employee operating in the public education system should feel a sense of belonging, act independently, think creatively, be self-aware, activate, manage, control and achieve a positive high result. It is necessary to achieve.

The rapid development of information technologies changes the conditions for the development of flexibility competence. With the possibility of online communication through special communication programs, conversations, forums, master classes, thematic video conferences, and seminars, the Internet helps the virtual unification of teachers of education in solving issues of flexibility competence development.

Each subject of education has its own needs for the development of flexibility competence of the teacher, because they are influenced by various factors: personality structure, interests, scientific, psychological, pedagogical and special training, level of general education; pedagogical experience, level of development, etc. are formed.

The effectiveness of the development of the flexibility competence of the teacher of education depends on the following psychological and pedagogical processes: if the need for the development of flexibility competence of the person is fulfilled, if the teacher of education can evaluate himself, if he knows the coefficient of flexibility and has the methods of analyzing the competence of flexibility, if he is ready for changes, he is focused on understanding his actions, feelings and analysis of his activities, if he has reflexive ability. As activity, as indicators of his personal characteristics, as his acmeological characteristics, allowed to distinguish several approaches.

In conclusion, it can be said that considering the concept of the development of flexibility competence in a separate position of activity or on the basis of a personal approach does not allow to see the phenomenon of the competence of development of flexibility competence as a whole special attention is paid to.

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